

1 Methodological considerations for studying exercise and training responses in youths

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7 Citation:

8 McKiel A, Falk B. Methodological considerations for studying exercise and training responses in
9 youths. Appl Physiol Nutr Metab. 2025 Jan 1;50:1-6. doi: 10.1139/apnm-2025-0122. PMID:
10 40811863.

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21 Key words: Children, Ethics, Exercise, Laboratory, Pediatric, Research Methods, Techniques

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23 Abstract

24 The study of exercise and training responses in children and adolescents involves
25 methodological challenges which are unique to this population. Such challenges include ethical
26 considerations, differences in body dimensions, maturational effects, differences in baseline or
27 resting characteristics, large signal variability, psychological considerations, and logistical
28 factors. Some challenges may be addressed using alternative measurement techniques, while
29 others can be addressed with modification of protocol design or statistical approaches. Where
30 possible, approaches to address these unique considerations for pediatric exercise research are
31 provided. Thus, this perspective may be a valuable resource for those considering, or those
32 already engaged in pediatric exercise science.

33

34

35 Introduction

36 The study of exercise science poses unique considerations specific to researching
37 pediatric populations. These include ethical issues, considerations related to body size and
38 variable maturity, physiological, and psychological considerations. Some, although not all these
39 considerations, can be moderated using non-invasive technology, protocol familiarization,
40 scaling, or other data analysis and statistical approaches (see Table 1). This perspective discusses
41 these considerations and where possible, solutions are provided. It provides scientists interested
42 in pediatric exercise science with pediatric-specific considerations and solutions.

43

44

[Table 1]

45

46 **Ethical considerations**

47 Ethical considerations in pediatric research have limited the use of many invasive
48 techniques, as well as the extent of exposure to physiological and environmental stress (i.e.,
49 exercise volume, heat, cold). Perceived psychological or emotional distress may also impact the
50 methodological techniques in youths.

51 *Invasive research techniques*

52 Some research techniques, such as tissue biopsies and indwelling/needle
53 electromyography (EMG) are invasive, involve some risk and are potentially painful. They are
54 thus inappropriate for pediatric research. Even blood sampling, which is potentially painful, is
55 often avoided with youth study participants. With advancements in technology, non- or
56 minimally-invasive alternatives exist (Armstrong and Fawkner 2008). For example, saliva
57 samples can be used to examine the *pattern* of the exercise response of some hormones (e.g.,
58 cortisol) typically measured in the blood (Adebero et al. 2020).

59 Non-invasive alternatives to muscle biopsies also exist. Muscle metabolism can be
60 reflected in oxygen uptake kinetics during step-transitions to various exercise intensities or with
61 ³¹P magnetic resonance spectroscopy (Armstrong and Fawkner 2008). Whole-body substrate
62 utilization can be assessed with orally-administered stable isotope tracers (e.g., ¹³C-labeled
63 glucose, or leucine, ¹⁵N-labeled glycine) measured in breath or urine samples (Mahon and
64 Timmons 2014). In fact, a “virtual biopsy” approach using ²H₂O, was recently used to examine
65 muscle-specific protein synthesis rates in youths with and without Duchenne muscular dystrophy
66 (Evans et al. 2021).

67 Similarly, indwelling/needle EMG – a technique used to assess motor unit activation
68 patterns – can be substituted with non-invasive surface EMG decomposition (Nawab et al. 2010;
69 Woods et al. 2024). High-density surface EMG decomposition may also be used to estimate
70 muscle fibre characteristics (Casolo et al. 2023).

71 Finally, many cardiovascular responses to exercise (e.g., cardiac output, blood flow,
72 oxygenation) have been successfully estimated in pediatric populations using non-invasive
73 techniques such as doppler ultrasound (Unnithan et al. 2018), bioelectrical impedance analysis
74 (Welsman et al. 2005), and near infrared spectroscopy (Callewaert et al. 2013).

75 *Stress exposure*

76 The severity of physiological stress exposure is another pertinent ethical consideration in
77 pediatric research. While youths can and do engage in high-intensity activities (Mota and
78 Esculcas 2002), including resistance exercise (Lloyd et al. 2014a), exercise/training volume
79 should be carefully considered during study design to avoid injuries that may affect the growth
80 and development of participants. Unavoidably, this results in training guidelines and
81 recommendations that are typically based on adults' experimental data or anecdotal pediatric
82 field reports. Likewise, in pediatrics, it is not possible to determine the maximal safe
83 environmental (e.g., heat, cold) exposure experimentally. Therefore, epidemiological data (Berko
84 et al. 2014) or field data (Rivera-Brown and Pagán-Lassalle 2024) are often used to infer safe
85 environmental exposure.

86

87 **Body dimensions and scaling**

88 An obvious challenge associated with assessing exercise responses in youths is separating
89 age-, intervention-, and dimension-related effects. Unlike adults, youths grow during longitudinal

90 studies, irrespective of experimental intervention, posing a unique challenge as there can be large
91 variability in the growth rates, even within a narrow age range (Malina et al. 2004). Therefore, a
92 control group is *imperative* in pediatric training studies, to account for growth-related changes in
93 exercise responses. Individual variability in growth rates can also be addressed statistically, using
94 multilevel (hierarchical) modeling with mixed/random effects (Armstrong and Welsman 2020).

95 Scaling can often account for dimension-related differences in exercise responses.

96 Scaling can be incorporated into a study's design or data analysis. Often, ratio scaling is used, in
97 which an outcome (e.g., $\dot{V}O_2$ peak, strength, power, metabolic heat) is simply divided by body
98 mass (Mercier et al. 1992; Armstrong et al. 1996; Dotan et al. 2013; Leites et al. 2016), or other
99 aspects of body size such as body surface area (Meade et al. 2019) or muscle size (McKiel et al.
100 2024). Nevertheless, although easy and convenient, this approach is only truly appropriate when
101 the relationship between the outcome (e.g., $\dot{V}O_2$ peak) and the scaling variable (e.g., body mass)
102 is linear – an assumption that is seldom met.

103 In cases of non-linear relationships between outcomes and scaling variables, allometric
104 scaling can be implemented (Welsman and Armstrong 2019), typically described as: *outcome* =
105 $a \cdot \text{scaling variable}^b$, where *a* and *b* represent the proportionality coefficient and allometric
106 exponent, respectively. This approach has previously been used in pediatric exercise research to
107 scale outcomes such as $\dot{V}O_2$ peak (Armstrong et al. 1998) and peak anaerobic cycling power
108 (Doré et al. 2001). Allometry can further be applied to longitudinal studies in combination with
109 multilevel modeling to determine the effects of growth and development (Armstrong and
110 Welsman 2020) and training (McNarry et al. 2014) on exercise outcomes. However, large sample
111 sizes are needed to accurately calculate allometric exponents as there can be significant inter-
112 sample variability (Welsman and Armstrong 2019). Ultimately, there is not a “correct approach”

113 for scaling. Rather, the ideal approach depends on the research question and the resources
114 available.

115 Scaling can also be incorporated into the design of a study. Prescribed exercise intensity
116 can be scaled and assessed relative to the maximal capacity of participants. Common examples
117 include scaling exercise intensity relative to maximal ability (e.g., % $\dot{V}O_2$ peak), although this
118 necessitates comparable effort levels between participants – a feat that is often difficult to
119 achieve in youths. Alternatively, exercise can be prescribed at an intensity relative to *a priori*
120 assessments of body mass and size. For example, exercise load has been prescribed relative to
121 individuals' body mass, to provide similar metabolic heat production between $\dot{V}O_2$ peak-matched
122 boys and men (Leites et al. 2016). Thus, the challenge of differing body dimensions and
123 proportions can be addressed through outcome scaling, appropriate statistical approaches and
124 thoughtful study design.

125

126 **Maturation effects**

127 Maturity status refers to the level to which an individual has progressed toward biological
128 maturity (Malina et al. 2015), and can be assessed in terms of pubertal stages (Tanner 1962),
129 menarcheal status, somatic maturity, or skeletal maturity (Lloyd et al. 2014b). Independent of
130 chronological age and body size, maturity has been shown to affect $\dot{V}O_2$ peak (Armstrong and
131 Welsman 2020), motor performance (Beunen and Malina 1988), and sports performance (e.g.,
132 soccer skills; Malina et al. 2005). Maturity may also affect the response to training and should be
133 considered in training intervention studies (Armstrong and Barker 2011; Lloyd et al. 2014a).
134 Since there is considerable interindividual variability in the tempo and timing of maturation
135 (Malina et al. 2004), it is imperative that the maturity status is considered in pediatric studies. At

136 a minimum, researchers should report maturity status and when possible, maturity should be
137 controlled for during study recruitment and/or data analysis.

138

139 **Baseline participant characteristics**

140 Over the lifespan, “baseline” physical characteristics and fitness change. For instance,
141 resting heart rate decreases (Sarganas et al. 2017) and resting blood pressure increases (Muntner
142 et al. 2004) from childhood into adulthood. In studying exercise- or training-related effects, age-
143 related differences in resting values should be accounted for by calculating changes relative to
144 pre-exercise/training values (Hebestreit et al. 1993) or by including baseline values as covariates
145 in the statistical analysis (Savage et al. 1986).

146 Physical fitness also changes from childhood into adulthood. $\dot{V}O_2$ peak, anaerobic power,
147 and muscle strength primarily increase with age in youths after allometrically controlling for
148 changes in body or fat-free mass, and to a greater extent in males (Nevill et al. 1998; Armstrong
149 and Welsman 2019, 2020). Further, physical activity levels decrease and patterns change during
150 the growing years (Mota and Esculcas 2002; Larouche et al. 2012), and these changes can be
151 influenced by numerous factors, such as biological sex and socioeconomic status (Craggs et al.
152 2011; Dumith et al. 2012). It is thus very difficult to match the “training status” and habitual
153 physical activity levels of participants of varying ages. To account for this challenge, researchers
154 must be explicit regarding the populations being assessed, report differences in baseline
155 characteristics, and assess the effects of pre-exercise/training differences.

156

157 **Signal variability**

158 Compared with adults, exercise responses in youths are often relatively small and more
159 variable resulting in drastically lower signal-to-noise ratios. This challenge is ubiquitous in
160 pediatric exercise science. For example, youths have more variable torque signals during
161 contractions, lower task accuracy, greater position variability, and more variable muscle
162 activation patterns compared with adults (Takahashi et al. 2003; Fox et al. 2014; Choi et al.
163 2023). Likewise, heart rate and gas exchange outcomes are more variable in early vs. late
164 pubertal children during cycling (Blanks et al. 2023).

165 Variability can be reduced through familiarization with task protocols and measurements
166 (Deutsch and Newell 2004). This approach is necessary but is often insufficient. Increasing
167 sample size can also compensate for high variability, although recruiting participants for
168 pediatric exercise research is often difficult (see **Logistical considerations**, below). Averaging
169 results of multiple bouts or implementing smoothing/averaging techniques into data reduction
170 improves the signal-to-noise ratio of many physiological measures (e.g., breath-to-breath $\dot{V}O_2$
171 measurements; (Armstrong and Fawcner 2008). Ultimately, additional recruitment and careful
172 study design, data reduction, and analysis are needed to observe true changes or group
173 differences in pediatric exercise research.

174

175 **Psychological considerations**

176 Exercise-related motivation, understanding, concentration, and perception change during
177 development, affecting recruitment and data collection. For example, high-intensity and/or long-
178 duration efforts may be distressing or unexciting for child participants, leading to suboptimal
179 efforts. Using age-appropriate reward systems (e.g., stickers for younger participants) and

180 providing additional verbal motivation during intense/long exercise may address this
181 psychological challenge.

182 Young study participants may also differ in their ability to understand instructions and to
183 maintain attention during long exercise testing sessions. Therefore, experimental protocols may
184 need to be modified, and sessions may need to be shortened. For example, multiple short-
185 duration sessions is typically favourable compared with few longer-duration sessions.

186 The perception of exercise intensity or effort changes as youths develop and mature
187 (Kasai et al. 2021) which is especially important when high effort is required. In some scenarios,
188 maximal outputs can be “confirmed” through supramaximal testing, such as with $\dot{V}O_2\text{max}$
189 (Sansum et al. 2019). However, with many short duration, “all-out” tests, such as Wingate
190 anaerobic test, no such confirmation is possible.

191 Most psychological considerations are at least partially addressed with substantial
192 familiarization built into the study design, which increases contact time with participants thereby
193 building trust, comfort, and better understanding of the exercise tasks. Subjective ratings of
194 perceived exertion during these sessions may be useful in coaching participants towards the
195 required effort. Thus, with appropriate study design, challenges related to motivation, attention,
196 and perception can be mitigated.

197

198 **Logistical considerations**

199 Laboratory- or field-based studies pose unique challenges when assessing youths. While
200 the laboratory allows for specific and controlled measurements, university laboratories are not
201 readily accessible to children. Youth participants often need to be actively recruited from local
202 youth organizations, clubs, teams, or schools. Additionally, scheduling youth participants can be

203 onerous, as it may involve the coordination of their school and after-school activity schedule,
204 their parents' schedule, and often the schedule of their sibling(s).

205 Field-based exercise studies are often carried out in schools or local clubs, allowing for
206 larger groups to be studied within a given time frame (e.g., Tanveer et al. 2025). These studies
207 are becoming more prevalent in pediatric exercise research, given their translatability to the real
208 world, and the rising prominence of non-invasive wearable technologies for assessing
209 physiological outcomes (e.g., smart watches). However, logistical challenges such as establishing
210 a working relationship with collaborating organizations or obtaining supplementary ethical
211 clearance (e.g., from school boards) add additional barriers to such investigations. Thus,
212 logistical factors are a prominent and often overlooked challenge in pediatrics. Ultimately,
213 additional resources (i.e., time and funding) are needed to overcome this challenge.

214

215 **Conclusion**

216 While the study of pediatric exercise science presents many methodological challenges,
217 many can be addressed. Non-invasive technology, substantial recruitment and familiarization,
218 and the use of scaling or other data analysis and statistical procedures may be used to alleviate
219 some of these challenges. Though it may be more challenging to study youths, we have seen
220 repeatedly that children and adolescents are not small adults – their responses to exercise
221 (Souron et al. 2022) and training (Dotan 2025) can be quantitatively and qualitatively different
222 from adults' responses. We cannot assume that a healthy child will respond like a healthy adult,
223 that a young athlete will respond similar to an adult athlete, nor that a child with a chronic
224 condition will respond similar to an adult with a similar condition. Therefore, to better

225 understand the effects of growth, development, and maturation on exercise and training
226 responses, we must rise to these challenges.

227

228 **Funding**

229 This work was supported by the Natural Science and Engineering Research Council of Canada
230 (B. Falk and A. McKiel).

231

232 **Competing Interests**

233 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

234

235 **Data availability**

236 No data are associated with this perspective. Additional references are available upon reasonable
237 request.

238

239

240 **References**

- 241 Adebero T, McKinlay BJ, Theocharidis A, et al (2020) Salivary and serum concentrations of
 242 cortisol and testosterone at rest and in response to intense exercise in boys versus men.
 243 *Pediatr Exerc Sci* 32:65–72. <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2019-0091>
- 244 Armstrong N, Barker AR (2011) The Elite Young Athlete. S. Karger AG
- 245 Armstrong N, Fawkner SG (2008) Non-invasive methods in paediatric exercise physiology. In:
 246 *Applied Physiology, Nutrition and Metabolism*. pp 402–410
- 247 Armstrong N, Welsman J (2019) Sex-Specific Longitudinal Modeling of Short-Term Power in
 248 11- to 18-Year-Olds. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 51:1055–1063.
 249 <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000001864>
- 250 Armstrong N, Welsman J, Winsley R (1996) Is Peak VO₂ a Maximal Index of Children's Aerobic
 251 Fitness? *Int J Sports Med* 17:356–359. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2007-972860>
- 252 Armstrong N, Welsman JO (2020) Traditional and New Perspectives on Youth Cardiorespiratory
 253 Fitness. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 52:2563–2573.
 254 <https://doi.org/10.1249/MSS.0000000000002418>
- 255 Armstrong N, Welsman JR, Kirby BJ (1998) Peak oxygen uptake and maturation in 12-yr olds.
 256 *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 30:165–9. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00005768-199801000-00023>
- 257 Berko J, Ingram DD, Saha S, Parker JD (2014) Deaths attributed to heat, cold, and other weather
 258 events in the United States, 2006-2010. *Natl Health Stat Report* 1–15
- 259 Beunen G, Malina RM (1988) Growth and physical performance relative to the timing of the
 260 adolescent spurt. *Exerc Sport Sci Rev* 16:503–40
- 261 Blanks Z, Brown DE, Cooper DM, et al (2023) Signal Variability Comparative Analysis of
 262 Healthy Early- and Late-Pubertal Children during Cardiopulmonary Exercise Testing. *Med*
 263 *Sci Sports Exerc*. <https://doi.org/10.1249/mss.0000000000003296>
- 264 Callewaert M, Boone J, Celie B, et al (2013) Quadriceps muscle fatigue in trained and untrained
 265 boys. *Int J Sports Med* 34:14–20. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0032-1316359>
- 266 Casolo A, Maeo S, Balshaw TG, et al (2023) Non-invasive estimation of muscle fibre size from
 267 high-density electromyography. *J Physiol* 601:1831–1850. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP284170>
- 268 Choi YJ, Chalatzoglidis G, Trapezanidou M, et al (2023) Adolescent boys who participate in
 269 sports exhibit similar ramp torque control with young men despite differences in strength
 270 and tendon characteristics. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 123:965–974.
 271 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-022-05130-y>
- 272 Craggs C, Corder K, Van Sluijs EMF, Griffin SJ (2011) Determinants of change in physical
 273 activity in children and adolescents: A systematic review. *Am J Prev Med* 40:645–658
- 274 Deutsch KM, Newell KM (2004) Changes in the structure of children's isometric force
 275 variability with practice. *J Exp Child Psychol* 88:319–333.
 276 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jecp.2004.04.003>
- 277 Doré E, Bedu M, França NM, Van Praagh E (2001) Anaerobic cycling performance
 278 characteristics in prepubescent, adolescent and young adult females. *Eur J Appl Physiol*
 279 84:476–481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004210100385>
- 280 Dotan R (2025) Children's V̇O₂max trainability deficit: A quantitative analysis and a qualitative
 281 hypothesis. *Eur J Appl Physiol*

- 282 Dotan R, Mitchell C, Cohen R, et al (2013) Child-adult differences in the kinetics of torque
283 development. *J Sports Sci* 31:945–953. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2012.757343>
- 284 Dumith SC, Gigante DP, Domingues MR, et al (2012) Predictors of physical activity change
285 during adolescence: A 3·5-year follow-up. *Public Health Nutr* 15:2237–2245.
286 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1368980012000948>
- 287 Evans WJ, Shankaran M, Smith EC, et al (2021) Profoundly lower muscle mass and rate of
288 contractile protein synthesis in boys with Duchenne muscular dystrophy. *Journal of*
289 *Physiology* 599:5215–5227. <https://doi.org/10.1113/JP282227>
- 290 Fox EJ, Moon H, Kwon MH, et al (2014) Neuromuscular control of goal-directed ankle
291 movements differs for healthy children and adults. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 114:1889–1899.
292 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-014-2915-9>
- 293 Hebestreit H, Mimura KI, Bar-Or O (1993) Recovery of muscle power after high-intensity short-
294 term exercise: Comparing boys and men. *J Appl Physiol* 74:2875–2880.
295 <https://doi.org/10.1152/jappl.1993.74.6.2875>
- 296 Kasai D, Parfitt G, Tarca B, et al (2021) The Use of Ratings of Perceived Exertion in Children
297 and Adolescents: A Scoping Review. *Sports Medicine* 51:33–50.
298 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40279-020-01374-w>
- 299 Larouche R, Laurencelle L, Shephard RJ, Trudeau F (2012) Life Transitions in the Waning of
300 Physical Activity From Childhood to Adult Life in the Trois-Rivières Study
- 301 Leites GT, Cunha GS, Obeid J, et al (2016) Thermoregulation in boys and men exercising at the
302 same heat production per unit body mass. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 116:1411–1419.
303 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-016-3400-4>
- 304 Lloyd RS, Faigenbaum AD, Stone MH, et al (2014a) Position statement on youth resistance
305 training: The 2014 International Consensus. *Br J Sports Med* 48:498–505.
306 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bjsports-2013-092952>
- 307 Lloyd RS, Oliver JL, Faigenbaum AD, et al (2014b) Chronological Age vs. Biological
308 Maturation. *J Strength Cond Res* 28:1454–1464.
309 <https://doi.org/10.1519/JSC.0000000000000391>
- 310 Mahon AD, Timmons BW (2014) Application of stable isotope tracers in the study of exercise
311 metabolism in children: A primer. *Pediatr Exerc Sci* 26:3–10
- 312 Malina R, Boucharde C, Bar-Or O (2004) Growth, maturation, and physical activity, 2nd edn.
313 *Human Kinetics, Champaign, IL*
- 314 Malina RM, Cumming SP, Kontos AP, et al (2005) Maturity-associated variation in sport-specific
315 skills of youth soccer players aged 13-15 years. *J Sports Sci* 23:515–522.
316 <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640410410001729928>
- 317 McKiel A, Woods S, Faragher M, et al (2024) Optimization of post-activation potentiation in
318 girls and women. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 124:2737–2747. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-024-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-024-05475-6)
319 [05475-6](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-024-05475-6)
- 320 McNarry MA, Mackintosh KA, Stoedefalke K (2014) Longitudinal investigation of training
321 status and cardiopulmonary responses in pre- and early-pubertal children. *Eur J Appl*
322 *Physiol* 114:1573–1580. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-014-2890-1>
- 323 Meade RD, Notley SR, D’Souza AW, et al (2019) Interactive effects of age and hydration state
324 on human thermoregulatory function during exercise in hot-dry conditions. *Acta*
325 *Physiologica* 226:. <https://doi.org/10.1111/apha.13226>

- 326 Mercier B, Mercier J, Granier P, et al (1992) Maximal Anaerobic Power: Relationship to
327 Anthropometric Characteristics during Growth. *Int J Sports Med* 13:21–26.
328 <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-2007-1021228>
- 329 Mota J, Esculcas C (2002) Leisure-time physical activity behavior: Structured and unstructured
330 choices according to sex, age, and level of physical activity. *Int J Behav Med* 9:111–121.
331 https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327558IJBM0902_03
- 332 Muntner P, He J, Cutler JA, et al (2004) Trends in Blood Pressure Among Children and
333 Adolescents. *JAMA* 291:2107–2113. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.291.17.2107>
- 334 Nawab SH, Chang S-S, De Luca CJ (2010) High-yield decomposition of surface EMG signals.
335 *Clinical Neurophysiology* 121:1602–1615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinph.2009.11.092>
- 336 Nevill AM, Holder RL, Baxter-Jones A, et al (1998) Modeling developmental changes in
337 strength and aerobic power in children
- 338 Rivera-Brown AM, Pagán-Lassalle P (2024) Hydration and Performance in Young Triathletes
339 During a Competition in Tropical Climate. *Pediatr Exerc Sci* 36:8–14.
340 <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2022-0148>
- 341 Sallis JF (2000) Age-related decline in physical activity: a synthesis of human and animal studies
- 342 Sansum KM, Weston ME, Bond B, et al (2019) Validity of the supramaximal test to verify
343 maximal oxygen uptake in children and adolescents. *Pediatr Exerc Sci* 31:213–222.
344 <https://doi.org/10.1123/pes.2018-0129>
- 345 Sarganas G, Schaffrath Rosario A, Neuhauser HK (2017) Resting Heart Rate Percentiles and
346 Associated Factors in Children and Adolescents. *Journal of Pediatrics* 187:174-181.e3.
347 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpeds.2017.05.021>
- 348 Savage M, Petratis M, Thomson W, et al (1986) Exercise Training Effects on Serum Lipids of
349 Prepubescent Boys and Adult Men. *Med Sci Sports Exerc* 2:197–204
- 350 Souron R, Carayol M, Martin V, et al (2022) Differences in time to task failure and fatigability
351 between children and young adults: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Front Physiol*
352 13
- 353 Takahashi CD, Nemet D, Rose-Gottron CM, et al (2003) Neuromotor noise limits motor
354 performance, but not motor adaptation, in children. *J Neurophysiol* 90:703–711.
355 <https://doi.org/10.1152/jn.01173.2002>
- 356 Tanner JM (1962) Growth at adolescence
- 357 Tanveer M, Asghar E, Badicu G, et al (2025) Effectiveness of a school-based physical activity
358 intervention on overweight and obesity among children and adolescents in Pakistan. *PLoS*
359 *One* 20:. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0317534>
- 360 Unnithan VB, Rowland TW, George K, et al (2018) Left ventricular function during exercise in
361 trained pre-adolescent soccer players. *Scand J Med Sci Sports* 28:2330–2338.
362 <https://doi.org/10.1111/sms.13258>
- 363 Welsman J, Armstrong N (2019) Interpreting aerobic fitness in youth: The fallacy of ratio
364 scaling. *Pediatr Exerc Sci* 31:184–190
- 365 Welsman J, Bywater K, Farr C, et al (2005) Reliability of peak $\dot{V}O_2$ and maximal cardiac output
366 assessed using thoracic bioimpedance in children. *Eur J Appl Physiol* 94:228–234.
367 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00421-004-1300-5>
- 368 Woods S, McKiel A, Herda T, et al (2024) Developmental changes in motor unit activity
369 patterns: child-adult comparison using discrete motor unit analysis. *Applied Physiology,*
370 *Nutrition and Metabolism* 49:904–919. <https://doi.org/10.1139/apnm-2023-0339>

Methodological Considerations	Possible Approaches	Resources and Examples
Invasive techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological markers → Saliva analysis • Muscle biopsies to examine metabolism → oxygen uptake kinetics, ³¹P magnetic resonance spectroscopy • Substrate utilization → stable isotope tracing • Motor unit activation → surface EMG decomposition 	<p>Adebero et al. 2020 Armstrong and Fawkner 2008</p> <p>Mahon et al. 2014 Woods et al. 2024</p>
Variable growth rates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical approaches (e.g., multilevel modeling) 	Armstrong and Welsman 2020
Body dimensions differences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scaling of exercise stimulus (e.g., %MVC) • Scaling of outcome measures 	<p>Woods et al. 2024 Welsman and Armstrong 2019</p>
Variable maturity levels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accounting for maturity in study design (or participant recruitment) • Statistically accounting for maturity in data analysis 	Armstrong and Welsman 2020
Resting values differences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Statistical approaches (e.g., using resting values as covariates) • Examining relative changes 	<p>Savage et al. 1986 Hebestreit et al. 1993</p>
Low signal-to-noise ratio and high signal variability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extra task familiarization • Signal smoothing • Increasing sample size • Averaging of repeated trials 	<p>Deutsch and Newell 2004 Dotan et al. 2013</p> <p>Armstrong and Fawkner 2008</p>
Psychological development/maturation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age-appropriate incentives or rewards • Age-appropriate motivation approaches • Shorter experimental sessions • Familiarization 	

373 *See text for specific examples and comments on the approaches.
374